

Synthesis of some New 4,6-Diaryl-5-aroyl-2-imino-6*H*-2,3-dihydro-1,3-thiazines

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It is reported that thiourea reacts with mesityl oxide in acidic medium to give 2-imino-6*H*-2,3-dihydro-1,3-thiazine and 2-thioxotetrahydropyrimidine derivatives¹. Similarly, 6-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-arylacryloylbenzo[*b*]furans on reaction with thiourea in alkaline medium afford 6-aryl-4-[5'-(6'-hydroxy-4'-methoxybenzo[*b*]furan)]-2-imino-6*H*-2,3-dihydro-1,3-thiazines². The reaction of 2'-hydroxychalcones in alkaline medium has been found to give 4,6-diaryl-2-imino-6*H*-2,3-dihydro-1,3-thiazines³. In the above reaction, the use of dimethylsulphoxide and sodium methoxide⁴ instead of aqueous KOH has reduced the reaction period from 3 h to 5 min. In the present study, 3-aroil-flavanones (**1a-j**) were allowed to react with thiourea in alkaline medium to give the corresponding 4,6-diaryl-5-aroil-2-imino-6*H*-2,3-dihydro-1,3-thiazines (**2a-j**) (Table 1).

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in a sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were run on an Unicam Sp 200G spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

4,6-Diaryl-5-aroil-2-imino-6*H*-2,3-dihydro-1,3-

thiazines (**2a-j**) : To a solution of **1** (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) were added thiourea (0.01 mol) and aqueous KOH (prepared from 0.02 mol KOH in small amount of distilled water). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h, then diluted with water and acidified with concentrated HCl. The products (**2a-j**) were filtered and crystallised from ethanol, (yields 60–70%); the compounds gave colouration with ethanolic FeCl₃ showing the presence of free phenolic OH; ν_{\max} 1680–1690 (C=N of imines)⁵, 3300–3400 (NH of imines) and 3200–3600 cm⁻¹ (non-bonded OH); δ (CDCl₃) 2.12 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 3.65 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.38 (1H, s, H_A), 7.21 (1H, s, H_B), 6.9–7.8 (12H, m, ArH), 7.8–8.4 (14H, b, NH), 8.73 (1H, s, NH) and 10.19 (1H, s, OH).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF
4,6-DIARYL-5-AROYL-2-IMINO-6*H*-2,3-DIHYDRO-
1,3-THIAZINES (**2a-j**)*

Compd. no.	R ₂	M.p. °C	
2a	R ₁ = CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	196
		4-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄	248
		3,4-O-CH ₂ -O-C ₆ H ₃	144
		2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	182
		2-Furyl	86
f	R ₁ = H	C ₆ H ₅	177
		4-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄	132
		3,4-O-CH ₂ -O-C ₆ H ₃	141
		2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	188
		2-Furyl	86

*Satisfactory analyses for C, H and N were obtained.

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